

UNEMPLOYMENT AND ITS CONSEQUENCES

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Abstract : *The article describes unemployment and its consequences, as well as the impact of the global financial and economic crisis on the market, the level of unemployment in some countries and its impact on the economy, ways to eliminate unemployment.*

Key words: *unemployment, frictional unemployment, structural unemployment, cyclical unemployment, natural unemployment.*

INTRODUCTION

Increasing economic instability exacerbates the manufacturing downturn, resulting in rising unemployment. Unemployment exacerbates economic instability and depression, exacerbating the crisis

In general, unemployment is caused by a decrease in production from the seasonal state of affairs when there is no demand for enterprise products and the enterprise is unable to adapt to changes in business conditions. Also, since the basic law of the market is competition, of course, this will develop enterprises that can meet the requirements of the market, and those who can not meet them will face a crisis, resulting in unemployment in these enterprises. It should be noted that the concepts of "unemployed population" and "unemployment" are often confused, as if there is no difference. However, the unoccupied population is different in its composition and should be viewed from two perspectives and divided into two groups

1. Not to be busy at will.
2. Not being forced to work.

Forced unemployment can be seen as the same as unemployment. What are the manifestations of unemployment? Typically, unemployment manifests as hidden and overt unemployment. Although they want to work, jobs are so limited that there are individuals who think the job search is futile, leading to hidden unemployment. Because these people were not looking for work, they were not registered as unemployed in state statistics. Despite the crisis in production, hidden unemployment still occurs even when state-owned enterprises try to keep their workers employed. In this case, the workers are still considered to be employees of the enterprise, but they are forced to work part-time or go on unpaid leave.

METHOD AND TECHNOLOGY

The reasons for the hidden nature of unemployment are:

- financing of industries and producers operating at some loss by the state;
- allocation of subsidies to bankrupt enterprises;
- In some countries there are enterprises with redundant labor, when the tax system is not perfect, which encourages their reduction;
- In cases where the property is monopolized. In an era of market economy, hidden unemployment and labor surpluses cannot be allowed to persist for long periods of time.

Declining demand, limited access to credit, improving the tax system, and other factors will eventually force workers to lay off, leading to transparent unemployment. There are a number of reasons why open unemployment occurs. Unemployment, for its own reasons, includes the main category of labor resources. There are the following transparent types of unemployment:

Frictional unemployment is temporary unemployment that occurs during a change of job, leaving the old job and moving to a new job. That is, they are a workforce looking for work. This category of the unemployed includes people who are changing their profession, moving, young people entering the work for the first time, those who are temporarily laid off. This form of unemployment exists in any social system, at any level of economic development, it is not considered socially dangerous unemployment. Structural unemployment is associated with the rapid

development of the economy, the development of science and technology, the emergence of new industries, qualitatively new industries, and at the same time the obsolescence of other enterprises, industries, technology. At the same time, new professions are constantly emerging and some previously common professions are becoming redundant, the demand for new professions is increasing and the need for old ones is decreasing. As a result, the labor force that has become redundant creates structural unemployment. There are certain similarities and differences in frictional and structural unemployment. The main difference is that in frictional unemployment there is a certain skill and experience, and it is possible to find a job in a short time. In structural unemployment, the workforce cannot find work immediately or in the short term. He must change his skills, retrain, get an education, get a profession. In some cases, you may even have to change your place of residence. Seasonal unemployment is the unemployment of those engaged in seasonal work at the end of the season, a type of unemployment specific to agriculture, construction, and tourism. Periodic unemployment is a decrease in the demand for labor as a result of a decline in production and the emergence of the unemployed. Periodic unemployment is one of the most serious economic and social problems of the market. People who want to work in periodic unemployment and who have the potential to do so are forced to become unemployed because the labor force is no longer needed by the economy due to the general decline in production. Institutional unemployment is created by labor market institutions. The main reason for this is that an unemployed person is able to live on a pension and therefore loses the incentive to look for work. Institutional unemployment occurs as a mass phenomenon when the amount of unemployment benefits is sufficient to meet the basic needs of the person, the period of payment of benefits is continuous. The consequences of institutional unemployment are not uniform. Of course, maintaining a decent standard of living for the unemployed, overcoming poverty and its social consequences is a positive thing, its negative side is the inefficient use of labor potential in society, the formation of a dependent spirit in citizens, the loss of motivation and motivation to work

CONCLUSION

Priority 4 of the Action Strategy is to gradually increase employment and real incomes, improve social protection and health care, increase women's social and political participation, build affordable housing, road transport, engineering and communication. and implementation of targeted programs for the development and modernization of social infrastructure, development of education, culture, science, literature, arts and sports, improvement of state youth policy, provision of pre-school education, general secondary education, secondary special and higher education implementation of measures to improve their quality and their development. According to the Action Strategy, it is planned to fully implement employment programs by creating 256.4 thousand jobs through the implementation of about 25,000 investment projects for the comprehensive development of the regions. It is planned to create 46.8 thousand new jobs in the regions with the highest unemployment rates, to provide loans to 10,000 graduates of educational institutions to start a business. Addressing the issues of creating effective and rational employment in the period of modernization of the economy, the compatibility of modern employment policy with the development of the labor market is one of the urgent tasks, and it is necessary to:

- continue to create new jobs and increase the efficiency of existing jobs;
- Continuous improvement of programs designed to take into account the number of those released from agriculture, new entrants and the unemployed;
- A number of measures should be taken to study the supply and demand for labor in the regions or to create and put into practice the theoretical basis for labor market coordination;
- to impose administrative measures on the heads of enterprises who did not inform about the available vacancies, to conduct inspections of existing vacancies at enterprises, to determine the reasons for their creation;
- Regular job fairs;
- Further increase the knowledge of those who want to be self-employed and entrepreneurs;

- Enhancing the effective use of the single window centers by entrepreneurs;
- further improvement of employment through the development of the automotive and textile industries;
- to study the level of labor migration in such areas to stimulate labor migration in densely populated areas, to assign tasks to determine the demand for labor in sparsely populated areas;
- retraining and employment of the unemployed, reducing unemployment;
- increase the share of employment in obtaining a job based on computer technology and appropriate means of communication "without leaving home";
- further improvement of the level of training in the field of economics and management, political science, social work, automotive;
- It is necessary to further expand the integration of the republic into the system of international division of labor, while further improving the entry into active international competition in industry, science and technology;
- maintaining a balance between the supply of labor resources and the number of jobs in the future;
- prevention of unemployment in local labor markets;
- Capacity building by further improving the system of training, retraining and advanced training in accordance with the period of modernization of the economy.

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